

A Mannan from the Kernel of Coconut (*Cocos Nucifera*)

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The kernel of coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) on extraction with alkali of different strengths yields polysaccharides containing galactose and mannose in different ratios. The one extracted by 18% alkali has been fractionated at acetylated and methylated derivative stages to yield a pure mannan. The structure of the mannan has been discussed.

Presence of a galactomannan and its structure in the kernel of coconut has been reported earlier¹. The galactomannan was obtained on extracting with hot water. Umeda and Hatano² have reported the presence of a mannan from the same source. Hence, an attempt was made to isolate the mannan by heating the water-extracted material successively with alkali of different strengths (0.4%, 4%, and 18%). The purpose of extracting with increasing strengths of alkali solutions is two-fold. One is that the polysaccharides of the same structural pattern having increasing molecular weights may be extracted with increasing strengths of alkali, the other being, that a polysaccharide of different structure having more solubility in higher strengths of alkali may be extracted. Possibility of both being simultaneously extracted by the same alkali solution may not be unlikely. The final strength of alkali is not allowed to exceed 18%, as above this concentration α -cellulose is soluble.

Extractions with alkali were carried out at room temperature in an atmosphere of nitrogen as alkali in presence of oxygen had a degrading effect on polysaccharides in general and especially on partially oxidised ones³.

As can be seen from the results (vide Experimental), the proportion of mannose increased in polysaccharides extracted with increasing strengths of alkali solutions. The polysaccharide extracted by 18% alkali separated into two fractions (D₁ and D₂) during electro-dialysis, one being soluble in water and the other insoluble. All the fractions were obtained as white amorphous powders. As the yields of polysaccharides D₁ and D₂ (for naming vide Experimental) were more and the mannose content was high, these were used for further investigations.

Polysaccharide D₂ was subjected to purification by repeated copper-complex formation⁴. The material obtained was found to become progressively richer in mannose. A constant ratio of galactose to mannose could not be obtained even after five purifications. The ratio obtained at this stage was 1:4:5 respectively, and as the amount of material went down to 0.75 g., no more experiments were tried on it. The increase in the pro-

1. Rao *et al.*, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 375.

2. *J. Agric. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1949, **23**, 65.

3. Banderet and Ronby, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, **30**, 1190.

4. Glandman and Timell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 1209; Chanda *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1289.

portion of mannose shows that the original polysaccharide is a mixture of galactomannan and mannan and the latter is being enriched during purification due to preferential precipitation of mannan to galactomannan.

Polysaccharide D₁ was acetylated⁵. After two acetylations the acetyl content reached 44.63%. The substance was then fractionated into six fractions by precipitating with methanol from a solution in chloroform. The ratios of galactose to mannose were determined in each fraction. Fraction D₆ was found to possess galactose to mannose ratio as 1:25.3, all other fractions showing higher amounts of galactose.

Fraction D₆ was methylated⁶ in tetrahydrofuran with dimethyl sulphate and solid sodium hydroxide with simultaneous deacetylation. The partially methylated substance was converted to fully methylated derivative by subjecting to Purdie's method⁷ of methylation. The material was dissolved in chloroform and fractionally precipitated by gradual addition of petroleum ether (60-80°) into four fractions. The first fraction D₆, on methanolysis and hydrolysis gave a mixture of methyl sugars. After demethylation of a small amount, paper chromatographic examination of the resulting mixture gave spots corresponding to mannose, indicating the fraction to be a pure mannan. Paper chromatography gave three spots corresponding to tetra-, tri- and di-*O*-methylmannose. The remaining material was separated into pure components on Whatman No. 3 MM filter sheets and the components eluted quantitatively with water. The tetra-, tri- and di-*O*-methyl sugars were obtained in the ratio of 1:7:1, indicating the length of the repeating unit to be 9 hexose units.

The 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-mannose fraction, $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 2.2^\circ$, was characterised as crystalline anilide, m. p. and mixed m.p. 143-44°. The tri-*O*-methyl fraction, having specific rotation -9.4° , was characterised as 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose by converting to crystalline 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose-1,4-di-*p*-nitrobenzoate, m.p. and mixed m. p. 190°. The di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose (OMe 29.6%) could not be characterised as no crystalline anilide could be prepared. The specific rotation differs from all known di-*O*-methyl sugars.

From these results it can be concluded that the mannose units in the polysaccharide D₆ are joined through 1 → 4 linkages and the mannan is highly branched. The negative rotation of the methylated derivative shows that majority of the linkages are of β -type.

It is of interest to note that the two specimens of homogeneous polysaccharides, viz., the galactomannan reported earlier¹ and the mannan (polysaccharide D₆), isolated from the kernel of the coconut, are both branched and that in both cases the repeating unit consists of nine hexose units. This shows that polysaccharides B and C are likely to be mixture of galactomannan and mannan.

Umeda and Hatano² have reported the isolation of a pure mannan fraction by extracting the kernel with 4% alkali. Contrary to these observations, no pure mannan could be

5. Carson and Maclay, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1015.

6. Haworth and Machemer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2279; Hamilton and Kiroher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4703.

7. Purdie and Irvine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **83**, 1021.

obtained in any of the fractions extracted by 0.4%, 4% and 18% alkali solutions; each fraction invariably gave both galactose and mannose on hydrolysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Paper chromatography was carried out by the descending method. For separation of small quantities of mixture, Whatman No. 1 filter paper and for large quantities, Whatman No. 3 MM paper were used. The following solvent systems (v/v) were used for chromatography.

- A. Ethyl acetate : pyridine : water (8:2:1).
- B. Butanolⁿ : ethanol : water (4:1:5), (upper layer).
- C. Methyl ethyl ketone-water azeotrope.

Saturated solutions of aniline oxalate in water and ammoniacal silver nitrate were used as spray reagents. Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out in *vacuo* at 30-40°. All the values of specific rotation given are at equilibrium.

TABLE I

	Polysacc. B.	Polysacc. C.	Polysacc. D ₁ .	Polysacc. D ₂ .
Sp. rotation (4% alkali)	-75.4°	-68.4°	..	-53.5°
Moisture (%)	0.99	10.4	11.48	10.95
Ash (%)	0.48	0.63	1.61	1.15
Uronic acid (%) ⁸	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Methoxyl (%) ⁹	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Pentosan (%) ¹⁰	0.2	0.25	0.35	0.31
Lignin (%) ¹¹	0.4	0.51	Nil	Nil
Ratio of Ga:Ma ¹²	1:2.44	1:2.09	1:4	1:3
Arabinose	Trace	Trace	Nil	Trace

Extraction of Polysaccharide Fractions with Alkali

The material, after extraction with hot water², was treated successively with alkali of different strengths (0.4%, 4% and 18%). In each case the material (100 g.) was shaken with NaOH solution (750 ml) for 16 hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The solution was squeezed through a piece of nylon cloth and centrifuged for clarification. The process of extraction was repeated and the combined extracts were acidified to pH 4-5 at a low temperature (5-10°). The polysaccharide was precipitated by adding the solution

8. Charles Doree, "The Methods of Cellulose Chemistry"; 2nd ed., Chapman & Hall Ltd., London, 1947, p. 391.

9. E. P. Clark, "Semimicro Quantitative Organic Analysis", Academic Press Inc., N. Y., 1943, p. 68.

10. Charles Doree, "The Methods of Cellulose Chemistry", 2nd ed., p 381.

11. *Ibid.*, p. 389.

12. Hirst and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1659.

to an equal volume of acetone with stirring. The material was collected at centrifuge, triturated with ethanol and ether, and dried. As the ash content of each fraction was high, the materials obtained by extracting with 0.4% and 4% alkali were subjected to dialysis in running water and that obtained by 18% alkali solution, to electro dialysis. During the electro dialysis a portion of the material went into the solution. The solution was filtered and the filtrate added to acetone when the polysaccharide was precipitated. All the fractions after precipitation were triturated as usual and dried.

The polysaccharides extracted by 0.4% and 4% alkali solutions were named as polysaccharide B and C respectively and the one extracted by 18% alkali solution and went into solution during electro dialysis as polysaccharide D₂; the one that remained undissolved was named as polysaccharide D₁. Table I shows the constants of each fraction.

Treatment of Polysaccharide D₂

Polysaccharide D₂ (1.9 g.), having galactose:mannose ratio as 1:3, was purified through copper-complex formation¹³ with Fehling's solution. The complex was destroyed with dilute acid and the polysaccharide precipitated with acetone. The purification was repeated five times, when the amount went down to 0.75 g. The proportion of galactose and mannose, after hydrolysis and quantitative estimation by paper chromatography, was found to be 1:4.5. The arabinose, originally present in traces, was removed. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -48.2° in 4% NaOH (c, 0.5).

Treatment of Polysaccharide D₁

Acetylation of the Polysaccharide².—Completely dried polysaccharide D₁ (4 g.) was dispersed in formamide (60 ml) by stirring for 6 hours at room temperature. Pyridine (100 ml) was added slowly followed by dropwise addition of acetic anhydride (80 ml) over a period of 2 hours, with stirring. After stirring for 24 hours, the thick blackish solution was diluted with glacial acetic acid (200 ml) and poured into ice-cold water through a fine cloth. The acetylated product, obtained in long fibres, was filtered on a sintered glass, washed till free of acid, and dried. The partially acetylated and dried product was subjected to a second acetylation by dissolving in pyridine (100 ml) and adding acetic anhydride in the same way as above. The more highly acetylated material was precipitated, washed, and dried; yield 3 g.; acetyl content¹³, 44.63%; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -49.31° in chloroform (c, 1).

Fractionation of the Acetylated Polysaccharide.—The acetylated polysaccharide (2.8 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (200 ml) and fractionally precipitated by adding increasing amounts of methanol. Six fractions were collected. A small portion of each fraction was deacetylated¹⁴ with 0.4 N EtOH-KOH. The polysaccharide liberated was hydrolysed with 2 N-H₂SO₄ and the components, galactose and mannose, were estimated. The results are recorded in Table II.

13. J. B. Niederl and V. Niederl, "Methods of Quantitative Organic Analysis", 2nd ed., John Wiley and Sons, Inc., N. Y., 1948, p. 252.

14. Peterson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2361.

TABLE II

Fraction.	Methanol added.	Subst. precipitated.	Sp. rotation.	Ga. Ma.
D _a	35 ml	0.37 g.	-55.0°	1:3
D _b	70	0.14	-73.3°	1:5
D _c	230	1.01	-61.9°	1:25.3
D _d	290	0.59	-42.1°	1:3.75
D _e	590	0.31	-41.2°	1:3
D _f	On evaporation	0.24	-39.7°	1:2.03

*One-step Methylation*⁶ of Fraction D_c.—Fraction D_c (0.9 g.) was dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (20 ml) and methylated with dimethylsulphate (15 ml) and solid NaOH (13 g.), the reagents being added in sevenths during 48 hours while shaking mechanically. After the addition of the second portion of the reagents, the mixture was refluxed for 1 hour to complete deacetylation. The flask was cooled and during the reaction tetrahydrofuran was added so as to maintain fluidity. Towards the end of the reaction the mixture was further refluxed for 1 hour. The cooled mixture was filtered and the precipitate extracted with chloroform. The filtrate was evaporated and extracted with chloroform. The combined extracts were washed with water, dried, and evaporated to dryness. The material obtained was purified by extracting with acetone (yield 0.7 g., OMe 41.7%).

Two additional methylations by Purdie's method⁷ were conducted on the same material when fully methylated polysaccharide was obtained (yield 0.62 g., OMe 45.37%); $[\alpha]_D^{30} -5.21^\circ$ in CHCl₃ (c, 1).

Fractionation of Methylated Polysaccharide D_c

The methylated product (0.61 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (20 ml) and petroleum ether (60-80°) was gradually added till a slight precipitate appeared. The material was removed at centrifuge, washed, and dried. Thus four fractions were obtained. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Fraction.	Pet. ether added.	Substance precipitated.	Sp. rotation (in chloroform).
D _{c1}	42 ml	283.7 mg	-12.89°
D _{c2}	53	69.3	+21.83°
D _{c3}	103	116.9	+24.8°
D _{c4}	On evaporation	107.7	+4.01°

Methanolysis and Hydrolysis of Fraction D_{c1}

Fraction D_{c1}, obtained in the above fractionation, was refluxed with 5% methanolic HCl (25 ml) for 16 hours. The syrup, obtained on evaporation, was hydrolysed by heating on a boiling water bath with *N*-HCl (25 ml) for 14 hours. The solution was neutralised,

filtered, deionised, and concentrated to a small bulk of syrup. The mixture on demethylation¹⁵ with hydrobromic acid gave only mannose together with partially demethylated sugars, when examined by paper chromatography.

Separation and Characterisation of the Component of Methylated Hydrolysate

The mixture, when examined by paper chromatography using solvent C, gave three spots corresponding to 2,3,4, 6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-mannose (R_f in solvent C, 0.85), 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose (R_f 0.50), and a di-*O*-methylmannose (R_f 0.25).

The mixture of methyl sugars (about 100 mg.) was separated on Whatman No. 3MM filter papers using solvent C. The syrups corresponding to tetra-, tri-, and di-*O*-methyl sugars were cut, eluted quantitatively with water, and evaporated to dryness. The weights are 12, 83.2, and 11.6 mg. respectively.

The tetra-*O*-methyl-D-mannose fraction, having $[\alpha_D]^{30} + 2.2^\circ$ in water (*c*, 1) (lit.¹⁶ $+2.4^\circ$; $+1.2^\circ$) and -OMe 52.1% (calc. for $C_{10}H_{20}O_6$: OMe, 52.5%), was refluxed with ethanolic aniline and the *N*-phenyl-2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-mannosylamine, obtained in the usual way, was crystallised from ether-petroleum ether (60-80°); m.p. and mixed m. p. 143-44° (lit.¹⁷ m.p. 142-43°).

The tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose:OMe, 42.1% (calc. for $C_9H_{18}O_6$: OMe₃, 41.9%); specific rotation -9.4° in water (*c*, 1) (lit.¹⁸ -10°), was treated with *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride in dry pyridine. The solution was heated at 67-70° for 30 minutes and kept overnight. The solution was neutralised with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The solution was extracted with chloroform (2 ml) thrice. The extract was washed with dilute acid and water and dried. The material obtained after removing the solvent was crystallised from methanol to yield crystalline 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose-1,4-di-*p*-nitrobenzate; m.p. and mixed m.p. 190° (lit.¹⁹ m.p. 191°); $[\alpha]^{32}_D + 34^\circ$ in chloroform (*c*, 0.5 (lit.²⁰ $+33^\circ$)).

The di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose fraction, having methoxyl contents 29.6%, did not form any anilide or isopropylidene derivative. The specific rotations $+12^\circ$ (in water) and $+40^\circ$ (in methanol) differ from all the known di-*O*-methyl-D-mannoses (2,3; 3,4; 4,6). The ratio of tetra-, tri-, and di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose is 1:7:1.

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15. Hough *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1702.
16. Green and Lewis, *Science*, 1926, **61**, 204; Irvine and Modie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 1462.
17. Irvine and McNicoll, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **97**, 1449.
18. Hirst and Jones, *ibid.*, 1948, 1278.
19. Prentice *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **81**, 684.
20. Rebers and Smith, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 6077.